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China's Green Engagement in Central Asia: Drivers and Limitations

Pulatov Khasan

East China Normal University, School of Politics and International Relations, 2st Year Master's Student

***Abstract:** The paper examines the drivers and limitations of Beijing's participation in renewable energy projects in Central Asia. The 20th Congress of the Communist Party of China, which adopted the 14th Fifteen-Year Green Energy Development Plan, reaffirmed Beijing's support for green development in China and beyond, including in Central Asia, which was identified as one of Beijing's strategically important and long-term cooperation partners in clean energy sphere. Beijing's growing interest in the green development in Central Asia is driven by several reasons, including new economic opportunities, geopolitical interests, as well as Beijing's international climate commitments. China's geographical proximity, leading position in the clean energy technologies and competitive prices for renewable energy products may contribute to strengthening cooperation ties between the countries of the region and Beijing in the development of the green economy in Central Asia. However, such challenges as growing competition among external players for new energy markets in Central Asia, the local context (balanced equidistance of the countries of the region from global centers of power in economic and technological terms), as well as Beijing's current economic priorities in the region (infrastructure development and resource extraction) all this affects the scope of possibilities for China's engagement in the development of renewable energy in Central Asia.*

***Key words:** China, Central Asia, energy, cooperation, green economy, energy security, sustainable development*

INTRODUCTION

China's 14th Fifteen-Year Green Energy Development Plan (2021-2025), unveiled in June 2022, is an ambitious plan aimed not only at further developing clean and safe energy, improving renewable energy production technologies, increasing energy efficiency, modernizing power grids and ensuring energy security, but also in combating climate change and ensuring a smooth transition to a green

economy.¹ Although initially the “green growth” strategy was seen as a policy oriented towards the domestic market, over time it has become largely aimed at developing green energy abroad. Thus, the basic principles of the renewable energy program in China are reflected in regional projects, in which, in particular, Beijing and the countries of Central Asia are directly involved (Statement of the SCO Council of Heads of State on Energy Security,² Green Investment Principle for the BRI³).

China's Energy Development Strategy identifies Central Asian states as one of Beijing's strategically important and potentially long-term partners in energy cooperation, and the "Renewed Partnership" within Regional Organizations includes China's systemic economic strategy focused on large-scale investments in the energy systems of Central Asia states, operating on renewable energy sources.

China and Central Asia: a new energy nexus

Today, Beijing is in an auspicious position with a robust internal market and a comparative advantage in investing in renewable energy projects. China's relative advantage lies in its significant experience in alternative energy supply chains. Beijing is a leader in clean energy production. Thus, Beijing produces more than 70% of solar panels and more than half of the world's wind turbines. The scale of new energy production causes its price to fall, making Chinese technology, equipment and materials relatively cheap on world markets compared to other foreign competitors, making it correspondingly attractive to potential customers. Today, China is the largest supplier of alternative energy equipment and a key engineering, procurement and construction (EPC) contractor for related energy projects.⁴

The demand for these technologies is enormous. The countries of Central Asia, actively participating in joint projects with China within the framework of the Belt and Road Initiative, are increasingly interested in ways to reproduce alternative energy sources, since at the present stage the countries of Central Asia, as they develop economically, have to face new problems. They are forced to cope with ever-increasing energy demands and rising fuel prices, while combating the effects of global warming. In light of new realities, the transition from traditional energy sources to new energy has become a fundamentally strategic approach for the countries of the region. Thus, the growing demand for attracting foreign investment in clean energy projects from developing countries of Central Asia, that are interested in decarbonizing their economies, acts as a key coupling factor.

Drivers

China's investment in the green economy of Central Asia is driven by several factors, including economic opportunities, geopolitical interests and international commitments to combat climate change (Paris Agreement).

Economic opportunities

The transition from domestic financing of clean energy projects to the export of green technologies and financing of related projects abroad, including in Central Asia, is dictated by a decrease in internal

¹ 14th Five-year plan for renewable energy development | China Energy Portal | 中国能源门户

² The state council information office, The Republic of China. “Leaders of SCO members states sign Samarkand Declaration”. Scio, 17.09.2022, http://english.scio.gov.cn/m/topnews/2022-09/17/content_78424919.htm#:~:text=The%20Council%20of%20Heads%20of%20State%20of%20the%20SCO%20issued,2030%20Agenda%20for%20Sustainable%20Development.

³ “Green investment principles”. Gipbr. <https://gipbr.net/Content.aspx?id=296&type=211&m=8>. Accessed 16 January 2024.

⁴ Ziyi Ma and Yu Ma. “What’s After Coal? Accelerating China’s Overseas Investment in Renewables.” World Resources Institute, 31 January 2023, <https://www.wri.org/insights/whats-after-coal-accelerating-chinas-overseas-investment-renewables>

subsidies in China, as well as new incentives for investment overseas, given the significant potential for the development of alternative energy sources, such as solar energy (2 billion kilowatts), hydropower (60-70 megawatts) and wind energy (2 billion kWh) in Central Asia⁵, which could lead to even greater financial benefits for Chinese projects in the relevant field, given the export of green technologies, knowledge and equipment to these countries of the region. Beijing sees economic benefits in financing “green economy” projects in Central Asia, as it provides an opportunity for Chinese enterprises to directly participate in improving infrastructure and implementing alternative energy projects in Central Asia, where China has already accumulated substantial experience in investing in green development projects in recent years. Thus, Chinese investment companies have provided financing for the construction of solar and wind projects with a total production capacity of more than 12,000 MW. in the region⁶.

The largest investments from China, amounting to hundreds of millions of dollars, have traditionally come from state-owned companies, which are the main source of funding for projects aimed at developing green infrastructure in Central Asia. However, at the present stage, Chinese private enterprises have become key players in the green energy sector in Central Asia, and state-owned companies have focused on foreign investment in traditional energy sources, which is explained by the fact that the CPC has actively encouraged private companies to invest more actively in green projects abroad and play a more key role internationally in the renewable energy sector.

Geopolitical interests

China's investments in the “green economy” are driven by its broader Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), which aims to expand connectivity and promote economic cooperation in Eurasia, and Central Asia plays a critical role in this strategy. As part of Beijing's support for its policies aimed at investing in clean energy programs in the region, the Chinese government is actively involved in financing infrastructure projects based on alternative energy sources, primarily solar and wind energy. Investment by Chinese companies in the wind and solar energy spheres in Central Asia provides these countries with many benefits, including saving on conventional energy sources, diversifying energy sources, and maintaining a steady flow of energy into the Chinese market.

Beijing's growing influence in the green energy sphere in Central Asia has serious repercussions for its degree of presence in the long term. The quick “enlargement” of Chinese enterprises in Central Asia allows Beijing to export “extra” production capacity, primarily in the field of solar and wind energy. Beijing's intention to improve its capacity to export superfluous solar and wind power comply with a surplus of equipment and technology in its internal market. Ultimately, Beijing's growing influence in the Central Asian region could lead to increased control over the clean energy market, forming barriers to entry for other players in the region. Such dynamics could establish Beijing's long-term presence and complete control over the renewable energy sphere in Central Asia. The availability of relatively inexpensive Chinese equipment for the production of green energy can be the main relative advantage in filling the new energy market with Chinese enterprises in Central Asia.

In addition, China's investments aimed at the new energy market will invigorate the Central Asian state's own energy supply security, while simultaneously decreasing the scope of Russia's impact in the

⁵ M. Laldjebayev, R.Isaev, A.Saukhimov. (2021). Renewable energy in Central Asia: An overview of potentials, deployment, outlook, and barriers'. Energy report 7, 3125-3136 DOI:[10.1016/j.egyvr.2021.05.014](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egyvr.2021.05.014)

⁶ CHRISTOPH NEDOPIL WANG. "CHINA BELT AND ROAD INITIATIVE (BRI) INVESTMENT REPORT H1 2021." GREEN FINANCE&DEVELOPMENT CENTER, 27 JULY 2021, China Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) Investment Report H1 2021 – Green Finance & Development Center (greenfdc.org)

region from an energy standpoint. China's investments in the renewable energy and its growing influence on the fossil fuels industry in Central Asia are lessening the efficacy of the Kremlin's energy leverage, preventing the rise of Russia's monopolization of the energy sector and incrementing energy security in Central Asia accordingly⁷.

International commitments

It is worth noting that Beijing's foreign investments in sustainable development projects are also aimed at implementing international obligations to protect the environment and advance the transition from fossil fuels to alternative energy sources. Beijing recognizes the expediency to tackle climate change problem and reduce carbon dioxide emissions into the atmosphere. Supporting a “green economy” in Central Asia demonstrates China's dedication to protecting the environment and enhancing “green” development practices. Both sides are striving to ensure transition to a low-carbon economy, which includes substantial investment in clean energy, carbon pricing and the improvement of green technologies.⁸ The reorientation from hydrocarbon fuels to renewable energy sources is an affirmative action for both the Central Asian states and China for a couple of reasons: saving limited resources, increasing energy security by reducing the necessity to import expensive fuel and reducing CO₂ emissions into the atmosphere.

Limitations

China's green “involvement” in Central Asia, as in many other regions, encompasses “green economy” projects, environmental agreements and initiatives to promote sustainable development. However, the scope and effectiveness of these efforts are affected by a number of limitations and challenges:

Clean Energy Competition in Central Asia

Chinese enterprises will have to compete with many other parties involved in the development of green infrastructure in Central Asia, such as the European Union, Middle Eastern countries, and Japan, which, unlike China, are investing in renewable energy projects in Central Asia for a long time. These countries prioritize environmental and social sustainability in their investments and often offer expertise in green technology and project management. It is also worth noting that the countries of Central Asia adhere to the principle of a multi-vector policy, including in the energy aspect, and try, as far as possible, not to fall into financial and technical dependence solely on one participant in the energy market⁹. Many potential partners willing to cooperate with the countries of the region in the field of new energy can contribute to the quick transition of Central Asia to new energy sources, providing an abundance of opportunities to attract external investment in the field of clean energy development, while avoiding the economic and technological dependence of countries on a specific player.

Ultimately, competition between other external actors and China in the development of clean technologies in Central Asia will help reduce the cost of such technologies, may encourage Chinese

⁷ Yunis Sharifli. “Eclipsing Russia: China’s green energy expansion into Central Asia.” *The China Project*, 18 July 2023, <https://thechinaproject.com/2023/07/18/eclipsing-russia-chinas-green-energy-expansion-into-central-asia/>

⁸ IRENA (2022), *China's route to carbon neutrality: Perspectives and the role of renewables*, International Renewable Energy Agency, Abu Dhabi.

Doi: [China's route to carbon neutrality: Perspectives and the role of renewables \(irena.org\)](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irena.2022.05.001)

⁹ Zhou, Yipeng. “Greener Pastures: China’s Clean Energy Engagement in Central Asia”, *RETCA Project*, Program on Central Asia, Davis Center for Russian and Eurasian Studies, doi: <https://daviscenter.fas.harvard.edu/insights/greener-pastures-chinas-clean-energy-engagement-central-asia>

investors to become more involved in energy projects, and will allow countries to prevent emerging parties from developing monopoly control over new energy sector.

Economic and strategic interests

China's main interest in Central Asia is often driven by economic and strategic considerations, such as securing energy resources and expanding the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). While green projects are part of this engagement, they may be secondary to these larger goals. Both China and Central Asian countries rely heavily on fossil fuels. Thus, the share of Central Asian countries in China's total natural gas imports is 1/3. Beijing continues to actively finance energy projects in the region based on the use of traditional energy sources (for example, the new branch D of the "Turkmenistan-China" gas pipeline is already put into operation this year¹⁰).

Beijing's investments in new energy development programs do not mean a complete abandonment of fossil fuels. This is a critical situation for the fossil fuel-dependent states of Central Asia and China, as an irrational shift away from fossil fuels will have devastating economic, social and political consequences for these countries. This principle is a distinctive feature of the Central Asian countries and China, which distinguishes them from most of the more radical climate change players who support stronger demands for reducing carbon emissions, such as the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD), which has decided to stop finalizing energy projects aimed at oil and gas exploration in 2021¹¹, and the joint statement of the SCO member states on their energy security adopted in Samarkand in 2022 de-facto stimulates investment in the oil and gas sector in order to ensure energy supply. The agreement was adopted taking into account the current realities and national interests of the states of the region, since the economies of the Central Asian countries remain heavily dependent on the production and export of fossil fuels.

Conclusion

Despite current challenges, China has already become one of the important directions in the Central Asian energy system and is likely to remain so in the future. China's goal to strengthen its leadership in green energy and its approach to achieving this goal will contribute to finding solutions for the energy transition and green development in Central Asia. Beijing's participation in financing energy projects in the region will play an important role in ensuring energy security and supporting economic development in the transition period of Central Asian countries. Thus, many energy projects are an attractive destination for clean energy development in Central Asia for Chinese investors and are already receiving enormous support from China. The Chinese government's goal of becoming a world leader in the development of renewable energy is consistent with the transition to a green economy in Central Asia, which means it will be able to expand the potential for regional cooperation in the field of green energy development, which can be realized by launching initiatives aimed at attracting Chinese investments in energy projects in Central Asia, the introduction of environmentally friendly technologies and equipment, as well as generally maintaining sustainable development in the region.

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